

How to Reionize the Universe: *Ionizing Photon Production and Escape in Extreme Starbursts*

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$$N_{\text{LyC}} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-3} = \rho_{\text{SFR}} \xi_{\text{ion}} f_{\text{esc}}$$

↑ Ionization rate ↑ Galaxies ↑ Production ↓ Escape

The Big Bang

$z \sim 10$

Reionization

$z \sim 6$

Credit: lunar.colorado.edu, Caltech

Which sources reionized the Universe?

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Faint galaxies:
Higher f_{esc} ?

e.g., Razoumov &
Sommer-Larsen 10
Wise+14

Bright galaxies:
Efficient SF, high ξ_{ion} ?

e.g., Wyithe & Loeb 13,
Schaerer+16, Steidel+16,
Nakajima+16

High Σ_{SFR} galaxies:
Compact? Threshold Σ_{SFR} ?

Borthakur+14

e.g., Clarke & Oey 02,
Borthakur+14, Alexandroff
+15, Sharma+17

Which sources reionized the Universe?

Ma+15,16

Too young?

Just right?

Too old?

Or LyC from
binaries?

<1 million years

3-5 million years
Wolf-Rayet stars?
Supernovae?

> 5 million years

LyC Searches – High z

- Increased IGM attenuation (e.g., Inoue+14)
- **Lots of low-z contamination!** (e.g., Vanzella+12, Mostardi+15, Siana+15)

LyC Searches – High z

F606W

fesc: 14-19%

Mostardi+15

> 51%

Shapley+16

> 50%

de Barros+16
Vanzella+16

28-57%

Bian+17

LyC Searches – Low z

f_{esc}: 4-10%
≤ 2%
3.3%

Bergvall+06
Grimes+07
Leitet+11

2.4%
4.5%

Leitet+13
Leitherer+16

1%

Borthakur+14

1.2%
2.5%

Leitet+13
Leitherer+16

LyC Searches – Low z

“Green Pea” Galaxies
Izotov+16a,b

The Green Peas

[O III] EW $\sim 200\text{-}2000 \text{ \AA}$
 $M_* \sim 10^8\text{-}10^{10} M_\odot$
 $s\text{SFR} \sim 10^{-9}\text{-}10^{-7} M_\odot/\text{yr}$
 $Z \sim 0.2 Z_\odot$
 $R_{UV} \sim 0.7\text{-}2.6 \text{ kpc}$
 $z \sim 0.1\text{-}0.3$

Cardamone+09
Izotov+11
Henry+15

Ly α

Henry+15
10/10 LAEs,
Low N_{HI}

Yang+17
28/43 with
EW > 20Å

Strong, narrow Ly α = LyC escape?
See talk by Erb

Verhamme+15
Dijkstra & Gronke 16

The Green Peas

Feedback?

Velocity dispersion: 100-250 km/s
FWZI ≥ 1000 km/s

The Green Peas

Pellegrini+12, Jaskot & Oey 13, Nakajima & Ouchi 14

[O III]/[O II]

High ionization
parameter?

Nebular He II
emission

- 54.4 eV

Jaskot & Oey 13

R23

Nakajima & Ouchi 14

High $[\text{O III}]/[\text{O II}] = \text{High } f_{\text{esc}}$?

Compactness = High fesc?

Possible scenario?

Compactness

Right Age

Outflows

Mrk 71

NGC 2366

B, R, H α

van Eymeren, López-Sánchez

Mrk 71

Knot A:

$$[\text{O III}] \ 5007, 4959 / [\text{O II}] \ 3727 = 21$$

$$[\text{O III}] \ \text{EW} = 2000 \ \text{\AA}$$

[O II]
[O III]
He II

Knot B

$10^8 L_{\odot}$ in IR,
1.5 pc radius

WR stars
5 Myr

Knot A
1 Myr

Binette+09

What do Green Peas have in common?

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Expect *lower* EWs
from optically thin
regions

e.g., *Bergvall+13; Jaskot &
Ravindranath16*

Observe *highest* EWs

e.g., *Kewley+15, Izotov+17*

What do Green Peas have in common?

Preliminary:

Jaskot & Ravindranath 16

Ravindranath+ in prep.

Young ages needed

(*Kewley+15, Izotov+17, Jaskot+in prep.*)

Binary models needed

(*Stanway+16, cf., Steidel+16*)

LyC Production

High ξ_{ion}

Scharerer+16, Izotov+17

High ionization parameters +

Hard spectra?

Higher $\xi_{\text{ion}}?$

Higher $f_{\text{esc}}?$

Nakajima+16

How do they differ?

Jaskot & Oey 14

cf., Vanzella+17

How do they differ?

How do they differ?

Likely LyC Leakers

Not Leakers

Jaskot & Oey 14

cf., Vanzella+17

Escape

HST GO-14080
Jaskot+ in prep.

Not all strong
leakers
cf., Rutkowski+17

Adapted from Verhamme+17

$[O III]/[O II]$

Lya:
GO-14080, Jaskot
+ in prep.

Production vs. Escape

Jaskot+ in prep.
cf., Trainor+16

Prospects

- More GPs at high z

See talks by *Khostovan, Silverman, Onodera, Hirschmann*

Low- z : bursts, High- z : continuous SF? (*Izotov+17*)

Khostovan+16

Ion 2: $f_{\text{esc}} > 50\%$

Vanzella+16

Prospects

- What fraction are LyC Emitters?
- Which parameters matter?
- Is this the only mode of LyC escape?

Shapley+16

Borthakur+14

To conclude

- **High LyC production is key**
- Extreme Green Peas:
 - ▣ Young, compact starbursts
 - ▣ High LyC and LyA production
 - ▣ LyC escape due to strong radiation + low column densities (in some)
- Need more quantification
 - ▣ What fraction are leakers? Which parameters matter?